

TRICYCLE OPERATION AND CRIMINAL ACTIVITIES IN UYO METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the contribution of commercial tricycle and criminal activities in Uyo metropolis. Mobility is an important tool to economic activity considering movement of people and goods from one place to another. The objectives were to find out how tricycle operation meets the transportation needs of Uyo resident, to examine how tricycle operation enhance employment generation within Uyo capital city and finally to identify the effects of criminal activities on tricycle operation in Uyo metropolis. The sample size for this study was 245 while the population was 427,873 using taro Yamani formular. The theoretical framework used for this study was the Strain theory by Merton 1968. This study adopted a survey research technique. The data used in this study were gathered from primary and secondary sources. The following hypotheses were tested; there is a significant relationship between tricycle operation and transportation needs in Uyo and there is a significant relationship between tricycle operation and employment generation. The study also discovered that Tricycle operation has really boasted the transportation needs and services by way of making it assessable to passengers and leading to comfort. The significant impact of tricycle introduction into the transportation system in the country cannot be overemphasized as it has significantly affected transportation for the commuters as they do not have to wait longer hours before getting a ride and it has some socio-economic importance in the area because it has created employment for the unemployed population, revenue generation for Government, employment for spare part dealers, and employment for mechanic respectively. Tricycle operation has really contributed and generated employment to not just graduate but citizens in Nigeria who would have remained unemployed and it was recommended that security agencies should be used, biometric registration of all tricycle operators should be taken into consideration so as to help reduce the criminal activities.

KEY WORDS: Tricycle, Operation, Transportation, Crime, Criminal Activities.

INTRODUCTION

Despite the socio-economic development of Tricycle operation in the nation, this mobility reliever had caused a lot of havoc/ crimes in different sectors of the country. The element that connects the transport sector with the overall economy is mobility. Interestingly, mobility is one of the basic features of economic activity as it underlines the basic need of economic agents moving from one location to another - a need shared by critical factors in the production, consumption and distribution spheres of the economy. Generally, in modern economy, providing mobility in an industry that offers services to customers, employs people, pays wages and salaries, invests capital and generates income. At the macroeconomic level, transportation and its component element of mobility is connected to a level of output, employment and income within a national economy (Udoh, 2014).

Tricycle remains an alternative means of transport for those who cannot access a convenient ride to their destination. More so, it also provides additional income and employment for those who do not have a formal job. Tricycle transportation in Nigeria was introduced in some major cities in the country and had even become alternative mode of transportation in urban cities of the nation where other modes of transportation like cars are found inaccessible due to poor terrain or absence of good roads (Udoh, E. 2022). Another benefit of the commercial tricycle business was the fact that since the riders followed people door to door, the simple exercise of walking from one's gate to the nearest bus stop was no longer undertaken and of course it was convenient (Ajiboye, 2017). In terms of affordability, in Uyo, for example, the amount a passenger is charged is always considerate in accordance to ones distances (Udoh, 2022).

In most cases the advantages of a tricycle include transport service, job creation, income generation and equity. It is fast, safer, economical and efficient mode of transportation. Transportation is the central point of the socio-economic development of nations. It is equitable in a sense that it can provide access and cheap alternative mode of transportation for passengers. This mode of transportation in terms of security wise, safety and risky is assured. One of the important distinguishing features of this mode of transportation is the level of flexibility of its operation, such that it has the ability of maneuvering on stalled traffic as well as travel on unpaved/rough roads. (Udoh, 2014)

The supple nature of its operation offers wide range of opportunities; it is a source of additional income for government and private sector workers who may take to it after closing from their official working hours as a driver or as an investor. Meanwhile, it is an important source of empowerment for the reserve army of unemployed youth on the streets and a cushion to reduce youth restiveness. Developing public transport system is to improve the level of service in terms of comfort, safety, and frequency in service as well as providing a reasonable and affordable fare for the public. (Declan 2012)

As the Commercial tricycle business is, riders and operators are confronted with several challenges. Critics of the commercial tricycle business maintain that the expansion of the business has increased the number of road accidents in the country. This has led to the loss of lives and in many cases permanent disabilities to victims. Another challenge confronting the Commercial tricycle riders or operators is the high cost of setting up the business. A prospective businessman willing to go into Commercial motorcycle/tricycle business would need between eight hundred to one million naira to start the business (Ajiboye and Dosunmu , 2007). This includes the cost of purchasing a tricycle (depending on the brand), the cost of registering or licensing it and registration with the riders' or owners, association. Given the

high cost of buying a tricycle, it is often difficult for new comers to raise sufficient fund to start commercial tricycle business.

Keke Napep riders are also reported to constitute nuisance on the highways since many of the riders do not obey traffic rules. As the size and population of a city grow, the demand for passenger's transportation gets more complex and difficult to satisfy. People begin to spend unnecessarily longer time in their bid to catch a vehicle to their destinations. Businesses suffer, school children get to school late, workers get to work late, and so many activities are jeopardized. In the end, this affect the general socio- economic condition of the people in Uyo and the nation`s gross domestic product at large. The situation came to a point that people started investing on private automobile as a way to seeking for a solution to the problem of transportation. To adequately put the tricycle business in its proper place in the economic history of Nigeria, it has become necessary to evaluate the contribution to the economy (Udoh, 2022).

Transportation is a basic necessity of man. In other words, transportation is not an end in itself, but a means to an end. As Armstrong, (2012) observed, urbanization is usually accompanied by an escalating demand for passenger transportation; with time, this demand gets more complex and difficult to satisfy. Ajiboye and Kolawole (2019) argued that urban transport services in Nigeria is inadequate both in qualitative and quantitative terms considering the rate of population growth and the economic condition of an average Nigerian on the affordability of transport services to meet his or her travel demands over the years. Tricycle (popularly called *Keke NAPEP* in Nigerian parlance) is one of the major alternatives adopted by the urban residents in Nigeria as a means of transport.

Tricycles are essential form of urban transport in many developing countries and a form of novelty transport (Levy and wong 2010). Depending on the country where they are used, their mode of use and circumstances surrounding their usage, names as Toktok (in Egypt), Pousse-Pousse (in Madagascar), Raksha (in Sudan) and keke Marwa or keke NAPEP (in Nigeria) have been used in describing tricycles. In Nigeria it is common to see the Indian Bajaj motorized tricycle conveying passengers and/or goods from their sources to their destinations. This means of transportation like all others has its long history of evolution.

The history of tricycle put briefly can be traced to the 17th century when a disabled German Stephan Farffler built a three-wheeled wheel chair for himself in 1655 in order to maintain his mobility. Being a watch maker he was able to create a vehicle that was powered by hand crank. It was in 1789 that two French inventors developed a three-wheeled vehicle, powered by pedals which they named tricycle (Wikipedia, 2015). As applied in this study the term tricycle refers to a three-wheeled vehicle based on the same technology as bicycles or motorcycles and powered by motorcycle or scooter engines or electric motor. This is known as motorized tricycle. The first steam (motorized tricycle and probably the first true self-propelled land) vehicle was Nicolas- Joseph Cugnot's 1769 Fardier Vapeur (steam dray), a three-wheeled machine with a top speed of around 3km/hr originally designed for hauling artillery (Wikipedia, 2015). Nigeria like many other (especially) developing countries greatly make use of motorized tricycles as private or public means of transportation. In this study the motorized tricycle will often be used as tricycle.

Tricycle as a means of transportation in Nigeria is directly traced to the government of Mohammed Buba Marwa, who was the military governor in Lagos State from 1996-1999. After being launched, tricycles came to be known as “keke Marwa” – a name that has persisted

till date. The word keke is directly derived from Yoruba, the dominant indigenous language in Lagos State (Ajiboye et al; 2019). However the popularity of tricycles across the nation can be attributed to the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) which was launched under the administration of President Olusegun Obasanjo to alleviate poverty and provide economic empowerment to the people. Thus the name keke NAPEP gained popularity across Nigeria ([http://NAPEPNigeria.org/programmes /the kekeNAPEP project](http://NAPEPNigeria.org/programmes/the%20kekeNAPEPproject)).

The use of tricycles in Uyo Local Government Area as a public means of transportation was given momentum following the ban on private and commercial use of motorcycles which took effect on July 9, 2012. This policy, among other reasons, had the objective of reducing road accidents caused by use of motorcycles recklessly, reduction in motorcycle-aided crimes, promoting orderly usage of road by traffic and providing a better source of income generation for former motorcyclists (Wikipedia, 2015).

Transportation is one of the factors for the socio-economic development of any nation. It caters for the mobility needs of people in cities and towns for their various human activities. As the city evolve, the demand for passengers and goods movement become more complex and challenging to satisfy. People begin to spend longer waiting time on the roadside or terminal to catch a vehicle to their destinations, and all other purposes of travel are defeated. Because of these challenges, commuters decides to resort to other modes of transport such as tricycle and motorcycles to access destinations that situate in non-motor able roads (Udoh 2022).

The tricycle has been in used in Asian countries as a mean of public transportation, especially in Indonesia, Bangladesh, Thailand and Philippine. In Philippine mainly, a tricycle is composed of a motorcycle fitted with a singled wheel sidecar or a unique motorcycle with two-wheel cabs to provide mobility needs for a fee (Mcquald et al; 2003). Unlike its counterpart which uses the scooter engine, particularly those in Nigeria, Japan and India. A tricycle has various names at different localities of the world for example in Accra they are called Pragma, Qingqis in Pakistan, Rickshaw in India. However, the acceptance of tricycle as a means of public transport is because commuters consider its safety, security, affordability, reliability, comfort and efficiency for their transport service choice (Wikipedia, 2015).

The tricycle is known as 'KEKE NAPEP' in Nigeria, and its introduction was as a result of the stagnant economy, high cost of acquiring new and semi-used vehicles, weak transport system, and high unemployment rate as well as the need to empower a large number of idle youths to reduce poverty level in the society (Ajiboye and Dosunmu, 2007). 'KEKE' is a word in the Yoruba language in Nigeria, meaning bicycle. The evolution and development of KEKE as a means of public transportation in Nigeria can be traced back to Brigadier General Mohammed Buba Marwa (Rtd), the Military Governor of Lagos State between 1996 and 1999. He was the first to launch tricycle to be used as commercial transport in Lagos State and Nigeria. After the launched, the vehicles were called 'KEKE Marwa' (Mgbemena, 2013).

However, KEKE became popular across the nation due to the tricycle's adoption by the National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP) programme of President Olusegun Obasanjo's administration to reduce poverty level and economically empower her citizens. Thus, KEKE NAPEP gained popularity across Nigeria (Mgbemena, 2013). Furthermore, this was also the beginning of the widespread use of KEKE as a means of public transportation in Nigeria.

Since then Tri-cycle (KEKE NAPEP) usage has grown in leaps and bounds. It has

become an essential means of intra-city transport in Uyo capital City. However, this growth did not limit the usage and growth of commercial motorcycles operation. According to Amalgamated Commercial Motorcycle Owners and Riders Association of Nigeria (ACOMORAN, 2019), the usage of tricycle (KEKE NAPEP) in Akwa-Ibom State increased in numbers and within 2017 and 2018 her registered member has risen from 3000 to 6000.

The use of tricycle has become dominating as a means for commercial transport service in Uyo capital City. For these, there have been many challenges facing the operators and commuters. These challenges among others include high accident rates and traffic congestion, difficulty in financing the purchase of tricycle, high operation cost and meeting up with revenue generation daily by drivers, timelines, safety, the effects of the task force activities as well as the level of the experience of the operators.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Uyo Local Government Area witnessed the ban of private and commercial motorcycle operation by the state government on 9th July, 2012 in an effort to ameliorate the rising crime rate that was experienced in the area. Tricycles (known locally as keke NAPEP), buses and cars were purchased by the state government and handed over to interested transporters at subsidized rates. This provision of subsidized vehicles was meant to provide commercial alternatives to motorcyclists whose livelihood legitimately depended on the transportation business (AKSG online, 2010).

Transportation is an age-long activity. Consequently, transport demand dates back to the history of man. However, it has been noted that the demand for efficient and effective means of transport has not been met with a commensurate supply of the service. Particularly, governments across the globe have not been able to provide its citizenry with adequate, convenient and affordable mass transport system. Therefore, as a result, people have devised alternative means of transporting themselves and their goods between their points of origin and destination. Tricycle is one major component of this peculiar alternative, that is, the par transit. Transport demand in different parts of the world is growing at a very rapid rate and this is borne out of the necessity for people to meet social and economic as well as political, religious and tourism needs. The problems of poor transportation in urban centres, couple with the relative inadequacy of mass transit systems have led to the development of paratransit as an alternative. Ajiboye (2017) viewed tricycles as „informal transport services“, while maintaining that they play a significant role as „gap fillers“. Thus, there is a need to study their economic impacts on their operators as well as the quality of service they render to the commuters.

Herrmann (2015) observed that although government has made tremendous efforts in tackling the problems of urban transportation within the Uyo municipality, yet the spate of insecurity and crime in the state may not be unconnected with the recent ban of motorcycle operation in the municipality. The problem of identification of spatial and temporal variations within road crime hot spot or tricycle-aided crime is crucial because according to Herrmann (2015) by developing variations spatially and temporarily of crime hot spots at micro level in a more comprehensive and understanding way, crime prevention and crime control specialists can have a greater impact on apprehending criminals, police resources allocation and planning, crime modeling and forecasting, and evaluation of crime prevention and crime control programs .

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To investigate how tricycle operation meets the transportation needs of uyo resident.
2. To examine how tricycle operation enhance employment generation within uyo capital city.
3. To identify the effects of criminal activities on tricycle operation in uyo metropolis.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

1. There is no significant relationship between tricycle operation and transportation needs in Uyo metropolis.
2. There is no significant relationship between the tricycle operation and employment generation.
3. There is no significant relationship between criminal activities and tricycle operation.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Many states government established mass transit outfits as a conscious effort to complement the services of the private transporters. Yet much is left to be desired in the provision of transport services. The situation came to a point that people started investing on private automobile as a way to seeking for a solution to the problem of transportation. This last step only succeeded in worsening the situation as traffic congestion became another source of problem in towns and cities. Although many people could not afford the private car, interest went towards the motorcycle while later became very fashionable as soon as people noticed that it enjoyed faster access of the roads. It came to a level that even those who had cars were attracted to own motorcycles because of the freedom of way the motorcycle controlled. This led to an unprecedented surge in the number of motorcycles in the cities and an uncontrollable case of traffic accidents. The traffic system became chaotic and a nightmare. (Biona 2008)

As a result of the foregoing experiences, some state governments placed a ban on the use of the motorcycle in their state capitals and quickly substituted it with the tricycle. Some state governments even went to the extent of floating the tricycle in fulfillment of government pledge to bridge the gap caused by the ban on motorcycle. As soon as this happened, virtually all those who were into commercial motorcycle transport, and many others who were unemployed went into tricycle transport business. This helped in creating jobs for the teaming unemployed Nigerians. Today, the tricycle has gained ground in our towns and cities, and has become another mode of transport on its own unique class. Its presence is gradually penetrating the rural areas and may turn out to become the private car of tomorrow especially in the third-world countries such as Nigeria (Clarke, 2013:28).

Operational Characteristic of Tricycle Service

Tricycle as an informal transport system has dominated other public transport means because of affordability (Nwaogbe et al., 2012) and employment provision to youths through NAPEP scheme. Some commuters prefer tricycle to taxi because of its readiness, accessibility and ability to drop off commuters at e very point (Agustin, et al. (2018). According to Aikin and Akude (2015), commuters save more money using tricycle for their mobility needs while the result of the study of Jing et al. (2019) shows that commuters agreed that service cost is relatively moderate and convenient to use the tricycle.

Safety and security of tricycle operation have become a significant concern of commuters. As a means of public transportation, the tricycle has been criticised of being unsafe, and it has been noted to be a significant cause of an accident on the major roads (Onyekakeyah, 2016). The manners in which the tricycle are manufactured, and the reckless natures of the riders undermine safety, however operating the tricycle in mixed traffic, low-speed modes like tricycle and taxis are often exposed to accidents (Nwaogbe et al., 2012, Agustin, et al. (2018). Dike (2012) carried out an empirical study on the use of tricycle as public transport modes in Nigeria cities, and the result revealed that its operation is neither safe nor affordable, however; it is comfortable and readily available.

The socio-economic wellbeing of tricycle to people

Tricycle operations have many benefits such as job creation to youths both direct (riders) and indirect (spare part dealers, and mechanics) and sources of income. Ismail et al. (2018) in their study on tricycle operation as an alternative of urban transport in Lokoja revealed that the monetary benefit accrued to KEKE NAPEP operators ranges from \$4.26-\$8.51 monthly. Their findings were supported by the study of Raji (2012) on the appraisal of Auto Rickshaw as poverty alleviation strategies in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria. Tricycles have helped in easing transport challenges in developing countries as well as in reducing time and resource wastage. For instance, a study by Aikins and Akude (2015) revealed that tricycles have helped in reducing all incidents of agricultural losses to a significant level in Nigeria.

They also maintained that because tricycles are always available and affordable to the low income earners, their goods are easily transported to their homes on time with the aid of tricycles; thereby reducing losses resulting from thefts, bushfires, animal destruction and physical damages to the barest minimum. Tricycles, known as “Keke” in Nigeria local parlance, are lightweight, flexible and open-sided vehicles designed to carry three adult passengers and a driver (Omoke *et al.*, 2019). Tricycles have been represented in the literature with a variety of names, namely low-cost transport (Ocampo, 1982), intermediate public transport (Iwata, 1995; Ume and Nwachukwu, 2011), paratransit (Shimazaki and Rahman, 1996) and informal public transportation (Cervero, 2000; Kumarage *et al.*, 2010). These studies maintained that paratransit serves as an alternative to mass transport.

It has been reported by Williams *et al.* (2019) that the widespread adoption of tricycles in the Northern part of Nigeria is because the driver is separated from passenger; thus, it preserved the religious ideals of sexual segregation of men and women. They noted that tricycles are popularly known as *Adaidaita Sahu* in Kano. *Adaidaita Sahu* is a Hausa word which means to straighten the line, or to maintain a queue. Just as Agbiboa (2017a; 2017b) observed the decorations of paratransit buses in Lagos (popularly known as *Danfo*), Williams *et al.* (2019) observed that tricycles in Northern Nigeria are decorated with a plethora of inscriptions locally known as *kwalliya* (beautification). This corroborates the earlier observation of Schulze (2012) who noted that the iconography of mosques, palm trees and swords that dominate vehicles in Northern Nigeria as an integral part of an Islamic paradigm that is associated to a typical religious visual culture in the north. Furthermore, Mukhtar *et al.* (2015) have argued that tricycle riding serves as an employment to many northern youths, thus serving as a means of poverty alleviation among the youths in the region. Similarly, some commuters expressed preference for tricycle as a means of transport because of its relative

affordability, availability and safety (Sun, 2009).

Tricycle in a Contemporary World

The tricycles are a powerful vehicle designed with a diesel engine, with a fuel tank capacity of 10.5 litres, and they have a passenger capacity of three to four people and payload capacity of 320kg. They also have adequate space for passenger luggage at the back and speed up to 80km per hour. The vehicle is basically suitable for intra-city commuting and commercial passenger having a low fuel consumption of 38km per litre. There is now petrol engine tricycle, with lower noise and lesser vibration, they are however smaller in capacity than the diesel counterparts, and it also produces cleaner exhaust fumes than the diesel engine tricycle.

The tricycle or the three-wheeler as some may call it assumes different names in most countries over the world, such as auto rickshaw, tuk-tuk, trishaw, auto rickshaw, auto rick, Bajaj, rick, tricycle, motor taxi or baby taxi in popular parlance is a potable kind of motor vehicle which is used on the road as a mode of transportation for either private or commercial use as the case may be, it can be used for passengers or for deliveries. It is a motorized version of the traditional rickshaw or relo taxi, a small three-wheeled cart operated by a single individual, and is a three wheeled cabin cycle. Srivinas (2015).

Tricycles are found in many developing and developed countries of the world. A tricycle is characterized by a sheet body or open frame resting on three wheels, a canvas roof with dropdown sides, a small cabin in the front of the vehicle for the driver, and seating space for three passengers in the rears, but in Nigeria today you will see passenger sitting by the driver side in order for the driver to make more money. It is generally fitted with an air cooled motorcycle engine; handle-bar control is fitted instead of a steering wheel. Human-powered tricycle is usually controlled with the use of pedals, although some models have hand cranks. Different modes of transport are available for urban commuters. These include taxi, city buses, trolleybuses, tram (light rail), passenger train, rapid transit, ferries, motorcycle and tricycle. The last two categories are the means of transport in developing countries designed to fill a gap created as a result of insufficient investment in urban transportation (Guillen and Ishida 2004 and Cervero, 2000).

The main objective of any transport policy at a global level is to achieve sustainable transport development. Sustainable transportation system connotes providing transportation needs that are economically viable, socially acceptable to meet safety and minimize consumption of non-renewable energy (Srinivas, 2015). In a null shell, these three concepts-economic, environmental and social system must be interconnected to achieve sustainable transport. This implies that transport services must be environmental friendly in such a way that the environment is not polluted with toxic substances emitted from exhaust pipes. Angira (2013) recommended walking and cycling as techniques for achieving sustainable urban transportation because cycling and walking do not make use of fuel. Within the perspective of an ecological, economic and social framework as proposed by Srinivas, in 2015, sustainable transport can be achieved through climate mitigation, energy efficient mode and urban planning through zoning techniques to reduce vehicular traffic.

In an assessment of the environmental effects of tricycle for urban transportation in the Manila area in Philippine, Cooper (2013) reported that tricycles were a source of air pollution and health hazards, according to him, a gasoline powered tricycle release over 10million tons

of Carbon-monoxide (CO₂) and caused more than 4,000 air pollution-related deaths on a yearly basis in the city. The Asian Development Bank as cited in Cooper (2013), estimates that for every 20,000 electric tricycles introduced to the city of Manila, the country saves 100,000 litres of fuel daily. This amounts to a savings of more than US\$ 35 million annually. In addition, the introduction of electric tricycle for urban transportation may likely reduce the emission of toxic substances into the atmosphere by 54%. Despite the disadvantages of fuel-powered tricycle such as emission of toxic substances, low carry capacity and advantages of an electric tricycle as highlighted above, it is yet to be introduced as a mode of transportation in urban centres in Nigeria.

Environmental Implications of Tricycles

Vehicles are one of the dominant sources of urban pollution in the developing world that threatens both people's health and economic activity (Asian Development Bank, 2005). Tricycles make up a sizeable number of vehicles in Nigeria and mostly have 2-stroke engines emitting fine particulate matter, which pose danger to public health. Epidemiological studies revealed that fine particles have serious health effects including premature mortality and such non-fatal effects as respiratory symptoms, exacerbation of asthma, and change in lung function (Kojima, 2000). Biona *et al.*, (2008) did a preliminary analysis on the fuel use and emission reduction potential of incorporating hybrid systems to two-stroke powered tricycles in Metro Manila, Philippines; it was discovered that 4-stroke provided the highest global warming potential when compared to carburetted 2-stroke, carburetted-hybrid 2-stroke, and direct-hybrid 2-stroke.

This could be traced to the high methane and CO₂ from these vehicles. 4-stroke tricycles also have the highest acidification potential (NO_x production) when compared to the rest. Another source of environmental pollution to be discussed is the diesel engine; According to Lloyd (2002), the environmental impact includes acidification potential (sources of NO production), soil and water pollution. Diesel engines generally release less carbon dioxide—the heat-trapping gas primarily responsible for global warming from the tailpipe which caused chronic bronchitis, asthma, reduced ability of the respiratory system to fight infections and remove foreign particles, and cancer (Monahan and Friedman, 2005). Another often unpopular source of pollution from tricycle is noise (unwanted sound); the World Health Organization suggests that noise can affect the human health and well-being in a number of ways, including annoyance reaction, sleep disturbance, interference with communication, effect on social behavior and hearing loss (ADB, 2005). Noise can cause annoyance and frustration as a result of interference, interruption and distraction. People experiencing high noise level differ from those with less noise exposure in terms of increased number of headaches, greater susceptibility to a minor accident, increased reliance on sedative and sleeping pills, and increased mental hospital admission rate. Exposure to noise is also associated with a range of possible physical effect including cold; change in blood pressure, other cardiovascular changes, problems with digestive systems and general fatigue. Further, there is fairly consistent evidence that prolonged exposure to noise levels can cause deafness (ADB, 2005).

Conceptualizing crime.

Violent and crimes such as murder, armed robbery, house burglary, kidnapping and

terrorism are the most inhumane that continue to plague Nigeria. Lately kidnappings for ransom and terrorism have taken the centre stage leading to blood shade and economic setbacks. The causes are farfetched as studies have associated rising youth joblessness to the increase in violent crimes. By using the deprivation theory proposed by Ted Gurr 1970 this study has explored the proximate and ultimate causes involving the youth in violent crimes. If factors that create the feelings of deprivation and frustration created by unemployment are addressed, Nigeria's youth will not be engaged in violent crimes. Joblessness is a situation where people are willing to work but cannot find any job, to this the use of tricycle is a key factor towards a successful operation. According to the international labor organization people who are without work but available for and seeking job, including those who have lost jobs and those who have voluntarily left jobs (World Bank, 1998).

On the other hand, crime is defined as a crime in which the offender uses or threatens to use violent force upon the victims. This entails (Wikipedia, 2010). Joblessness appears to be the root causes of violence whereby the use of tricycle is mainly used in Nigeria.

Researchers have suggested that joblessness is disproportionately more likely to be perpetrated, as well as victims of crimes and violence (Okafor, 2011). The growing gap between the rich and poor affects the society through criminal activities. The self-employed are in quandary as scant infrastructure makes it impossible for them to play their trade (Okafor, 2011). This is exacerbated by political corruption, poverty, poor governance, increasing population, and lack of policy initiatives and implementation to some extent encouraged criminal groups to thrive across Nigeria. According to the deprivation theory of Ted Gurr (1970) one of the classical theorists' explains why people engage in violence (riots, rebellion, coups, murder, and many other criminal activities). It examines the psychological causes involving frustration and aggression as the primary source of humane capacity for violence. Frustration is neither necessary nor sufficient leads to violence but greed may drive to violence. Frustration is a much stronger motivating force and prolonged frustration may cause greater probability for aggression.

The rise in violent crimes (robbery, kidnapping, thuggery, terrorism) committed by jobless youth is a sign of 'gap' in the society. The society already has its expectation for individuals and has established means of achieving them when the means are limited as the youth joblessness. People are forced to achieve the goals through illegal means to fulfill societal expectations (Peters *et al.*, 2023). Kidnappings are on the increase across Nigeria and the unemployed youths view the business as lucrative. They are available for recruitment, by politicians. In the northern part, they are recruited both by politicians and religious groups like "boko haram" to be used in political, religious, and terrorism acts. In Uyo metropolis, they find easy employment in petty criminal activities. The culture most at least accept, if not approve, actions as a means to an end. This could be the reason why suicide bombing is exclusive to the northern part of the country as violence is encouraged by some Islamic sects. Political violence is also likely if the current leadership and or the socio-economic and political system are seen as illegitimate. Security is a contextual issue which no state in the international system consigns to the periphery; it is a core-value that makes the state relevant in the international system (Ndifon, *et al.*, 2012). Crime activities have been increasing in many parts of the state taking into consideration Uyo metropolis with the use of tricycle. The causes are not farfetched as studies have associated rising youth joblessness to the increase of violence crimes in Nigeria. The accelerating level of conflict, divorce, rape, prostitution, armed

robbery, terrorism and all facets of violence, can be largely attributed to the incidence of unemployment.

The problem of violence crime in Nigeria has been exacerbated by the motivating factors which makes the environment conducive taking into consideration the use of tricycle. Bennel (2002) argued that urban societies are becoming increasingly criminalized, especially with the proliferation of youth gangs. Neither homes nor market are safe in Nigeria because of frequently occurrence of armed robbery incidents. Joblessness problems, which now seemed beyond remedy, has produced “army of idle hands” and some of them decided to punish the society that fails to provide with them means to livelihood and dignity by robbing its members of their property at gun point (Ideyi, 2005).

The police cannot perform effectively because they are over stretched by the amount of cases that awaits them daily, and its worsened by outdated instruments they use that are no match to the modern sophisticated weapons used by the criminals. The Research Director of the Nigeria Economic Summit Group (NESG), sope Williams Elegbe (2011) revealed that “the increasing poverty in Nigeria is accompanied by the increasing of joblessness and unemployment which is higher in the urban areas taking into consideration Uyo metropolis. Mix this situation with the radical Islamic sects, which promises a better life for martyrs, and you can understand the growing violence in the north. Government statistics shows that the northern states have the highest proportion of uneducated persons. If you link a lack of education and attendant lack of opportunities to a high male youth population, you can imagine that some areas are actually a breeding ground for terrorism” (Oxford Research Group, 2012). The inspector general of police, Muhammed Abubakar, (2012) has called on the three tiers of government to tackle these illegal arrangements in order to reduce crime rate in the county. He expressed concern at the rate youth were resorting to crime as an alternative means of survival due to unemployment.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Strain theory

Strain theory also predicts a link between economic deprivation and youth violence, since such deprivation is considering being an important form of strain. Merton (1968) is the proponent of this theory. He observed that many societies placed a high premium on economic affluence and social ascent for all of its members. Merton is careful to point out however, that such “innovation” is only one among other possible responses. Relative deprivation may also be considered to be a type of strain. While individuals may feel relatively deprived of a number of things (example like status, right, political power e.t.c.), feelings of relative deprivation due to economy can be important motivator of crime. This indicates that economic deprivation also reduces social trust and facilitates social disorganization which in turn leads to youth violence and crimes. It may also affects community and family in such a way that youth violence increases. The different theoretical approaches cited above offer plausible reasons why poverty, inequality, relative deprivation and other indicators may be related to youth violence. It is important to note that as some of theories imply, that different economic predictors may operate in entirely different ways, thus, the causal mechanism that link each other to crime may be differ. Conflict theories focused on the brutalization of the lower class and the contradiction of capitalist social disorganization theory considers informal social deterrent to crime and the impacts of economy factors upon these. Strain focused on pressures

to commit crime, while economic theories focused on cost / benefit analysis and incentives to commit crime. Relative deprivation theories focused on the recognition of one's inequality and subsequent feelings of resentment and frustration. The above indicates that economic deprivation intersects with a number of other theories, some of which are treated in details in other sections. But this section will therefore, focuses on poverty, joblessness, inequality as causes of youth crime and violence. The feelings of Allen (1996) also support the critic's argument. Allen (1996) using 1959 – 1992 uniform crime report and other data, examined the impacts of poverty, unemployment and inequality or robbery, burglary, murder etc. This consistent with the Marxist argument that elites use the criminal law to define the activities of the lower class as criminal, while ignoring the derivative activities those in power, (Chamambliss and Seidman, 1982).

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The use of tricycle (KEKE NAPEP) to eradicate the poverty level has improved the socio-economic condition of Uyo residents as well as causing a lot of havoc in the city. The outcome of this study is that customers are not too comfortable with the service offered by operators which are in line with the works of Chona *et al.* (2019), Nwaogbe *et al.* (2012), Ismail *et al.* (2018), Starkey *et al.* (2019) and Dike (2012). However, despite the challenges the commuters face on public transportation generally in Uyo, they are satisfied with the overall services of the KEKE NAPEP compare to other alternative means.

The significant impact of tricycle introduction into the transportation system in the country cannot be overemphasized as it has significantly affected transportation for the commuters as they do not have to wait longer hours before getting a ride and it has some socio-economic importance in the area because it has created employment for the unemployed population, revenue generation for Government, employment for spare part dealers, and employment for mechanic respectively.

CONCLUSION

From the study, it can be concluded that Tricycle operation has really boasted the transportation needs and services by way of making it assessable to passengers and leading to comfortably. Again during the raining season movement cannot be put to a halt, the introduction of the tricycle which came immediately after the barn of motorcycle in Uyo Metropolis has really reduced the accident rate.

Tricycle operation has really contributed and generated employment to not just graduate but citizens in Nigeria who would have remained unemployed. Although this tricycle operation has affected the society positively but it's an avenue of which arm robbers used in achieving their plans.

RECOMENDATIONS

From the research work, the following recommendations were made.

1. The use of biometric registration should be made for all tricycle operators so as to detect a particular tricycle involve in criminal activities and fetch out those who are involved.
2. The entrance of the tricycle should always be made open and the leather covering

should be removed so as to make it easy for the commuters to easily alert the public in case of any such act by the operators.

3. Provision of parking space; Many commuters sometimes get stranded at the park due to unavailability of a tricycle, thereby resulting in longer waiting time which the drivers attributed to insufficient parking space as the trickling down effect of traffic from the park sometimes result to traffic gridlock on the major or access road. The park will serve as a checking point for all operators so as to safeguard against any criminal activities.
4. The security Agencies should also be linked to the tricycle park, biometric registration with their checking strategy so as to checkmate some criminal activities.

REFERENCES

- Ajiboye A. O (2017). Comparative analysis of sources of finance of commercial motorcycle operation in urban Nigeria: A case study of Ago-Iwoye and Ogbomoso in Badejo, B. (eds), Nigeria and Sustainable Transportation- Issues and Agenda for Development. Gratia Associates International, Ijebu-Ode, 110-116.
- Ajiboye A. O. & Dosunmu V. A. (2007). Analysis of the sources of finance of micro, small, and medium-scale transport enterprises in Nigeria. The case of commercial motorcyclists. *The Interface: A Biannual Journal of Management* 3(2): 75-85.
- Ajiboye, A. O. & Kolawole, O. J. (2019). Addressing the issue of Tout (Agbero) towards Sustainable Road Public Transport in Ibadan. *Nigerian Journal of Logistics and Transport (NJLT)*, 1(1): 31-44.
- Armstrong-Wright, A., (1987). Urban transport the World Bank, a view. In: Heraty, M.J. (Ed.). *Developing World Transport*. Grosvenor Press International, London, pp. 302-305.
- Aryeetey, E. and Kanbur, R. (2008). *The Economy of Ghana. Analytical Perspective on Stability, Growth & Poverty*. Published by James Currey & Woeli publishing services.
- Declan, D, N. (2012). An Empirical Study of the Use of Tricycle As A Public Transport Mode In Nigerian Cities. *Journal of Social Sciences and Public Affairs Volume 2, Number 2, 2012*©Insuderc Academic Publishers.
- Hoyle, B. S. (1973). *Towards a Theory of Transport and Development*. Transport and Development © Macmillan Publishers Limited 2012.
- Kanemoto, Y. (2006). *Urban Transport Economic Theory. A Companion to Urban Economics* Edited by Richard J. Arnott, Daniel P. McMillen Copyright © 2006 by Blackwell Publishing Ltd.
- Kumar, R. (2010). *Research Methodology. A Step –by –Step Guide for Beginners* 3rd edition. SAGE Publications Ltd. 55 City Road. Nigeria.
- Levy, P. and Wong, W. (2010). *Nigeria's Transportation system*. Published by Benchmark Books
- McQuald, R. W., Cooper, J., and Smyth, A. (2003). *The Importance of Transport in Business'* Mgbemena, (2013). *Tricycle operation and criminal activities in Nigeria: unpublished Thesis*. Namdie Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Atai people. *International Journal of Education and Science Development* 2 (1): 27 – 44
- Peters, M. I., Usoro, N. A., James, A. C., Emeh, P. and Oyebanji, A. (2023). Substance Abuse and Deviant Behaviours among Ibibio Youth: Latent Dysfunction in Selected Communities IN Ed.: I. V. O. Modo, Kingdom, S. Mboho, Umoh E. Umoh. and

- a Ekaette R. Udoh.. in Academic Practitioners Research for Sustainable Development Goals in Africa. *International Centre for Integrated Development Research*. Ikot Ekpene, 50 – 58p.
- Udoh E. and Mboho (2022) *Community Development and Socio- economic Development of Rural Dwellers in Akwa Ibom State.Problem and Prospect*. Journal of Social and Management Sciences, Akwa Ibom State University, vol 1, No.2
- Udoh E. (2014) The Effect of Unemployment on conflict occurrences in Eket Local Government Area